

Geometry and Physical-Mechanical Properties of Rock Massifs with Underground Structures

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The geometry of underground structures has a profound impact on the metric properties of rock massifs, leading to local metric and dimensional changes that influence both local and macroscopic characteristics in the surrounding area. By incorporating fractal structures and functions, more realistic models for rocks and underground structures are developed. These fractal elements significantly affect effective physical-mechanical properties, particularly elastic modules, through the percolation effect, linked to the presence of scattered or concentrated fractures within the assessed volume. Understanding the fractal dimension and percolation threshold allows the derivation of analytical relationships describing elastic modules concerning damage concentration near this critical threshold. The study introduces the Weierstrass fractal model, designed to analyze horizontal underground excavations while accounting for surface roughness. This model facilitates stress distribution evaluation and stress concentration estimation near excavation profiles. Utilizing statistical mechanics to calculate fractal parameters provides continuum estimates for various aspects, including fractal density distribution and dimensions characterizing excavation contour roughness. It also identifies shear microstresses where fractal functions lack differentiability. Factoring in non-differentiability in fractal models offers insight into the complex changes in metric properties compared to traditional smooth models for underground excavations. Considering fractal properties when calculating effective physical-mechanical properties reveals their dependency on the fractal dimension across material concentrations. The fractal model aids in describing the process of microcrack aggregation into a through-crack as a percolation phenomenon, pinpointing the percolation threshold and its influence on effective elastic properties in the vicinity.

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1. Introduction

Classical models in mechanics of continuous media are closely linked to field theories, including, for example, gravitational and elastic fields [1–3]. In these models, the field arises from the potential generated by matter distributed in space [4–6]. In Newtonian models, spaces with

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different metrics were regarded as a collection of diverse objects. These objects create potentials in space, resulting in corresponding forces such as gravitational, elastic, and electromagnetic forces. The models developed by Riemann, Bolyai, Lobachevsky, and other researchers for non-Euclidean spaces are not directly associated with the distribution of matter [7–9]. Objects with fractal geometry have the additional effect of locally altering the dimensionality of space, resulting in fractional dimensions [10, 11]. As a consequence, objects with finite volumes are bounded by surfaces with infinite areas [12–14]. Similarly, artificial structures, such as buildings and large-scale engineering projects on the Earth’s surface, also impact the metric properties of the surrounding space, including the surface relief.

Underground constructions, serving various purposes such as mineral extraction and the development of underground spaces in megacities, further influence the metric properties of the subsurface environment [15]. The disintegration processes occurring in rock massifs near underground mine workings and the subsequent accumulation of damage in the disturbed massif can be described using fractal mechanics principles [16, 17]. Fractalization processes give rise to percolation phenomena [12], enabling the quantification of critical damage concentrations that trigger plastic or brittle failure processes [18]. When the concentration reaches a critical value, a structural transition occurs from a solid state to a discrete or granular state, imparting entirely new properties and characteristics to the fractured (disintegrated) rock mass [19, 20].

The formulation of continuum mechanics equations (CM) based on the non-Newtonian approaches extends the classical equations of continuum mechanics by introducing an invariant form applicable to any coordinate system [21]. The equations of motion and continuity in classical CM, expressed as partial derivative equations in Cartesian coordinates, are replaced by invariant derivatives [5]. The stress tensor in

classical CM is substituted by the generalized energy-momentum tensor or kinetic stress tensor, which allows the equations of motion and continuity to be written in an invariant form in any four-dimensional space. The classical Saint-Venant compatibility equations, for example, in the Einstein approach are replaced by the zero-reversal conditions for the six components of the Einstein curvature tensor associated with the Riemann-Ricci curvature tensor [22]. In the case of a linearly elastic medium, the generalized Hooke’s law serves as the constitutive equation, where the elastic moduli depend on the metric tensor of the space (medium) [23]. The model of a classical inhomogeneous linear-elastic body is equivalent to a space (medium) characterized by Finsler metrics [22, 24]. Consequently, the formulation of CM equations based on the Einstein approach enables the generalization of continuum models used in the mechanics of various materials, including rocks and rock masses [25]. For instance, the continuum dislocation theory model allows for the description of discontinuities, providing solutions to various problems in the field of physical plasticity theory [24, 26].

In this study, a Weierstrass fractal model considering surface roughness is developed for analyzing horizontal underground excavations. The model enables the assessment of stress distribution and estimation of stress concentration near the excavation profile. Fractal models account for the influence of material objects on metric, dimensionality, and physical properties.

2. Models of inhomogeneous and anisotropic mediums in Euclidean space

Currently, the predominant models used to characterize deformation processes in geomaterials and geotechnical systems are those developed for quasi-isotropic and quasi-homogeneous mediums [14, 27]. It should be noted that a geotechnical system refers to the combined “rock massif – engineering underground

structure along with all its components” [28]. In such models, heterogeneity can be addressed by considering material coefficients that depend on spatial coordinates. This approach adequately captures the relationships between stress and strain states, effectively described by a generalized Hooke’s law [29]. The relationship between stress and strain states can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \lambda_{ijkl}(\bar{x})e_{kl}. \quad (1)$$

This leads to the differential equations of motion balance in the form [14, 30, 31], expressed as:

$$(\lambda_{ijkl}(\bar{x})u_{k,l})_{,j} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial t^2} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the medium density; $\lambda_{ijkl}(\bar{x})$ are elastic modules; u_i are displacement vector components; σ_{ij} and e_{ij} are components of the stress and strain tensors, respectively.

In general, there is a lack of analytical methods for solving differential equations with variable coefficients in Eq. (2). However, different approaches, such as averaging methods, can be used to transform the local Eqs. (1), (2) into equations for averaged stress and displacement fields. In the general case, these equations form an infinite system of unclosed recurrence relations, which can be resolved by introducing additional hypotheses regarding the behavior models of geomaterials or geotechnical systems and their stress-strain states (SSS).

When modeling the material coefficients $\lambda_{ijkl}(\bar{x})$ as random statistical isotropic homogeneous fields, the effective dynamic modules (\bar{x}) can be represented as integral operators with different kernels. These kernels are products of Green tensors and correlation functions of elastic coefficients. Consequently, the effective elastic medium, which serves as an approximation of the real medium, is described by equations derived from Eqs. (1), (2) by replacing the elastic coefficients with effective operators [14, 27, 30, 31] expressed as:

$$\langle \sigma_{ij} \rangle = \hat{\lambda}_{ijkl} * \langle e_{kl} \rangle, \quad (3)$$

$$(\hat{\lambda}_{ijkl} \langle u_k \rangle_{,l})_{,j} = \rho \frac{\partial^2 \langle u_i \rangle}{\partial t^2}. \quad (4)$$

Here, \hat{x} denotes an integral operator, and the symbol $x * y$ is a convolution operation.

It is worth noting that the convolution operation used in this context bears a resemblance to the viscoelastic analogy, wherein elastic coefficients are substituted with viscoelastic operators [27, 32, 33]. For static processes, when assuming strong isotropy, the integral operators can be transformed into effective elastic modules. Approaches have been proposed to calculate these effective modules, considering the dispersion of module values across different materials [14, 26]. These approaches are well-explored for quasi-homogeneous media at the macroscopic level. Likewise, approximate solutions for anisotropic media have been developed, demonstrating the effectiveness of the effective medium model, particularly for quasi-isotropic media [31].

It has been established that an elastic inhomogeneous space possesses a non-Euclidean metric [14, 21]. In the most general case, the resulting model is described by Finsler metrics [14]. In the continuum theory of dislocations, the discontinuum exhibits Riemann geometry [24]. The presence of natural or artificial objects within the medium alters the curvature of space, thereby influencing the geometry of energy flow transmitted through waves, diffusion, and filtration mechanisms. This in turn affects the redistribution of stresses and strains within the medium.

The mathematical language developed by Newton and Leibniz effectively addresses most problems arising from relatively smooth fields of physical and geometrical objects [4, 5, 7–9]. However, the shift towards a world with objects of fractal geometry, pioneered by Mandelbrot, necessitates the development of tools that describe our surroundings more realistically. The local irregularity (unsmoothness) of real objects impacts the dimensionality of space, which can become fractional. This implies that local geometry influences global geometry, manifesting as a spatial fractional dimension characterized by

Hausdorff-Besicovitch self-similarity [12, 13, 34].

The dimensionality of self-similarity can be obtained as:

$$D = -\frac{\ln(N)}{\ln(l)} \tag{5}$$

where N is the number of equal elements within the object (cluster); l is the size of each element.

If the element is linear and is a linear unit, then $N \times l = 1$; if the element is a unit square, then $N \times l^2 = 1$; if the element is a unit cube, then $N \times l^3 = 1$. Here, D is the dimensionality of self-similarity, expressed as $D = 1, 2$ and 3 .

Rock massifs typically exhibit a complex structure, often characterized by cluster formations. These cluster structures can have well-defined boundaries or appear as fuzzy structures, which can be identified using fuzzy logic methods [8]. By examining the relationship between fractal dimensionality and the zigzag pattern of excavation contours, it has been observed that the fractal dimensionality (D) of “saw-like” contours with triangular and trapezoidal prongs is equal to 1.26. However, in the former case, less energy is expended in contour formation, making the realization of the first type of contour more likely [34]. If the contours of the cluster are defined, then an algorithm for determining its dimensionality can be adopted as proposed in references [12, 35, 36].

Thus, the calculation of averaged characteristics such as the center of mass, dispersions (moments of inertia, centrifugal moments of inertia), asymmetry, correlation functions, and correlation radiuses is carried out according to the usual formulas of mechanics, probability theory, mathematical statistics [12]. On the basis of these formulas, the fractal dimension is calculated, the value of which is used in finding the effective physical and mechanical properties of rocks and critical values of the values at which percolation occurs.

To apply the methods of links and nodes, the three concentric circles with radiuses are calculated and expressed as $r_0 = \langle r \rangle, r_0 - \sigma, r_0 + \sigma$ (σ is standard deviation, $\sigma = \sqrt{D}$, where D is dispersion). Thus, the main volume (area) is

concentrated between the contours ($r_0 - \sigma$) and ($r_0 + \sigma$). The average angle distance between the prongs is the order of the prongs.

Applied to the mechanics of rocks and underground structures, the calculation of the effective characteristics of the contour of an underground excavation is reduced to the construction of a smooth contour (circle $r = r_c$) passing through the found centers of mass of the fractal prongs and two coaxial circles of radiuses $r_c - \sigma$ and $r_c + \sigma$, forming a ring in which the fractal contour fluctuates, as shown in Fig. 1. Line 1 indicates the averaged contour of the excavation cross-section of the reduced radius $r = 1$; Line 2 indicates RMS contour of the excavation ($r - \sigma$); Line 3 indicates RMS contour of the excavation ($r + \sigma$). Fluctuations extending beyond the contours ($r_c - \sigma$) and ($r_c + \sigma$) are sources (concentrators) of stresses. Their average number and probability of outliers are calculated by the known formulas of probability theory.

The Hausdorff-Besicovitch fractal dimension is determined by the measure of space M_D , which quantifies length, area, and volume using the following equation [12]:

$$M_D = \sum \gamma(D) \delta D \tag{6}$$

where $\gamma(D)$ is a coefficient that depends on the geometry of the covering object [12, 34].

The limit of the measure M_D (at $\delta \rightarrow 0$) is not equal to 0 or ∞ , and it will be equal to the Hausdorff-Besicovitch dimension D_* , expressed as:

$$M_D = \sum \gamma(D) \delta D = \gamma(D)N(D)\delta D \xrightarrow{\delta \rightarrow 0} \begin{cases} 0, D > D_* \\ \infty, D < D_* \end{cases} \tag{7}$$

An essential characteristic of cluster fractality is the observation that its density decreases according to a power law as the characteristic size increases, expressed as:

$$\rho(r) = \rho_0 \left(\frac{r}{r_1} \right)^{(D_* - d)} \tag{8}$$

FIG. 1: (Color online) Fluctuation of the contour of the excavation cross-section.

where ρ_0 is the material density of cluster particles, r_1 is average particle size (radius), d is the Euclidean dimension of space.

Rock massifs undergoing artificial impacts, such as underground mining, and those experiencing post-mining periods undergo geometric phase transitions. To explore the behavior of geotechnical systems during these transitions, the application of percolation theory appears promising. This theory allows for the description of processes like plastic and brittle fracturing of rock massifs, filtration mechanisms, and fractalization. Note that percolation is a critical phenomenon characterized by non-analytical properties of the primary system variables near the phase transition point [12, 34].

An analytic function at a point x_0 can be expressed as a classical power series in the vicinity of that point. If a function $f(x)$ can be represented as such in the vicinity of a point x_0 , it can be expressed as:

$$f(x) = f_0 + f_1(x - x_0) + f_2(x - x_0)^2 + f_3(x - x_0)^{1.3} + f_4(x - x_0)^{1.8}. \quad (9)$$

The first three terms denote the analytic part of the function, and the last two terms denote the non-analytic part of the function.

The principal term $f_3(x - x_0)^{1.3}$ is called the critical or principal (singular) part, expressed as: $f(x) = [f(x)]_{\text{sing}} = \hat{S}_x f^\infty(x) f_3(x - x_0)^{1.3}$. The decomposition of functions in Eq. (9) describes critical phenomena, including the formation of primary cracks resulting from the merging of microcrack clusters [12, 36]. Determining critical points, known as percolation thresholds, indicating the concentration of damage at which infinite cluster (crack) formation occurs, can largely be achieved through statistical modeling. Representing field quantities in the form of generalized power and trigonometric series allows for numerical estimates, such as the probabilities of destruction near the percolation threshold, expressed as power dependencies with fractional exponents associated with the fractal dimensionality of space [37]. The fractional nature of the exponent implies that the function itself and its derivatives are non-differentiable in the classical sense. Multiple series of various kinds can be constructed based on the relationship between the Euclidean space dimension and the Hausdorff–Besicovitch dimension.

The main percolation models encompass lattice, cellular, and continuum models [12], which consider nodes, bonds, cell filling, rigid, and intersecting elements. The universality of percolation models arises from their ability to capture the connectivity of clusters, displaying scale similarity (“scaling”) in their topology near the critical region of transition from local to global connectivity [13].

Percolation transition signifies a geometric phase transition, with the percolation threshold or critical phase concentration demarcating two phases: one characterized by finite clusters and the other by a single infinite cluster [13, 36]. Cluster characteristics, like the correlation radius and the average number of nodes near the transition point, are described by exponential functions with distinct critical exponents. When studying clusters, fractals, and percolation, researchers derive nine specific characteristics [12], as follows:

1. N is the total number of cells;

2. $\langle N_s \rangle$ is the average number of clusters of size s ;
3. $n_s(p) = \langle N_s \rangle * N^{-1}$ is the distribution of clusters by size;
4. $\sum_s n_s(p)$ is the total number of occupied cells, expressed as: $\sum_s n_s(p) = e^{-hs} \alpha^{T\delta-1}$;
5. $sn_s(p)$ is the number of occupied cells belonging to clusters of size s ;
6. $w_s = \frac{sn_s(p)}{\sum_s n_s(p)}$ is the probability that a randomly chosen occupied node belongs to a cluster of size s ;
7. $S = \sum_s s w_s = \frac{\sum_s s^2 n_s(p)}{\sum_s s n_s(p)}$ is average cluster size, expressed as:

$$S(p) = \sum_s s^2 n_s(p) \alpha - |p - p_c|^\gamma; \quad (10)$$

8. $P_\infty(p) = \frac{N_\infty}{N_{occupied}}$ is the probability that a randomly chosen node belongs to the pulling cluster, obtained as:

$$P_\infty(p) = \sum_s sn_s(p) \alpha - |p - p_c|^\beta; \quad (11)$$

9. $\xi^2(p) = \frac{2 \sum_s \langle R_s^2 \rangle s^2 n_s(p)}{\sum_s s^2 n_s(p)}$ is a radius (length) of correlation, obtained as:

$$\xi(p) = \alpha |p - p_c|^{-\nu}. \quad (12)$$

The indices in the expressions (10)–(12) are universal, as they solely rely on the dimensionality of the problem space, expressed as:

$$\alpha = 2 - B\nu = 2 - 2\beta - \gamma, \delta = \frac{\gamma}{\beta} + 1, \quad (13)$$

$$\eta = 2 - \frac{\gamma}{\nu}, 2\beta + \gamma = \nu D$$

where D is the Euclidean dimension of space.

The following characteristics are also obtained as:

$$\langle \bar{r} \rangle = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i=0}^s \bar{r}_i \quad (14)$$

where $\langle \bar{r} \rangle$ is the radius vector of the cluster center. Then, the correlation radius R_s is obtained as:

$$R_s^2 = \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i=0}^s (\bar{r}_i - \langle \bar{r} \rangle)^2. \quad (15)$$

The equations (10)–(15) are similar to equations for calculating the random distribution of granular materials.

3. Alteration of the metric and dimensionality of the rock massif with underground construction

Consider a scenario where the rock massif contains underground structures like mine workings, and the dimensions in one direction are large enough to allow for a two-dimensional problem formulation. In such cases, the rock massif with underground structures can be viewed as a cluster, satisfying condition Eq. (8). The development of underground structures, as seen in mineral deposit operations, alters the metric properties of the surrounding space [15], thereby affecting the stress-strain state within the rock massif. The fractal nature of the underground structure influences its dimensionality, leading to changes in the effective properties of the rock massif. The corresponding numerical characteristics of the modified underground space are calculated according to the formulas given in the references [27, 30].

The focus is on the two-dimensional formulation of the problem, with a specific investigation of changes in the stress-strain state near an underground cavity within the rock massif. The contour of the cavity can be represented by a fluctuating curve, describable using fractals like the Koch or Weierstrass fractal [14, 15]. It should be noted that the length of the cavity contour can be infinite, while the area of the cavity remains finite. Despite the absence of external loads on the contour, the presence of irregularities leads to the generation of stresses in the surrounding region due to

the occurrence of stress concentrators. Then, the radius of a smooth contour is denoted as r_0 , which is a circle around and the real contour $r(\theta) = r_0 + \xi H(\theta)$ fluctuates continuously. As the unit normal to the actual contour moves along the free surface contour, it also undergoes fluctuations. The average contour, coinciding with $r_c(\varphi)$, corresponds to a circle with a radius $r_0 = r_c$. To evaluate the influence of fractality on stresses, the equilibrium equations are expressed in the polar coordinate system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial \sigma_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r}(\sigma_r - \sigma_\theta) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} = 0, \\ \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}}{\partial r} + \frac{2}{r} \tau_{r\theta} = 0. \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Note that the classical formulation is utilized to construct the analytical solution for determining the deflection of stresses in the rock massif with a deep underground cavity (excavation) [27]. The boundary condition on the cavity contour is expressed as:

$$\sigma_{ij} n_j = 0. \quad (17)$$

The equation (17) can be decomposed by the parameter ϵ because the unit vector of the normal n fluctuates discontinuously along the boundary in its direction. Thus, Eq. (17) can be expressed as:

$$\bar{n} = \bar{e}_r - \epsilon \frac{\bar{e}_\theta}{r_0} \frac{dH}{d\theta}, \quad \frac{\bar{e}_\theta}{r_0} \frac{dH}{d\theta} (\sigma_r^{(0)} + \epsilon \sigma_r^{(1)}) \bar{e}_r = 0 \quad (18)$$

where $r_0 = \text{const}$; \bar{e}_r and \bar{e}_θ are unit vectors directed along the coordinate lines of the polar coordinate system $(\bar{e}_r, \bar{e}_\theta)$; $H(\theta)$ is ring size of the radius fluctuation of the excavation contour radius; $\sigma_r^{(0)}$ and $\sigma_r^{(1)}$ are radial components of the stress state for the smooth and perturbed contour, i.e. the components of the stress tensor σ_{ij} are represented as:

$$\sigma_{ij} = \sigma_{ij}^{(0)} + \epsilon \sigma_{ij}^{(1)}. \quad (19)$$

Substituting Eqs. (18), (19) into Eqs. (16), (17), the boundary problems for the smooth contour and the fluctuating part for the varying contour are obtained as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r^{(0)}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r}(\sigma_r^{(0)} - \sigma_\theta^{(0)}) = 0, \quad (20)$$

$$\sigma_r^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_0} = 0, \quad \tau_{r\theta}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_0} = 0; \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_r^{(1)}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r}(\sigma_r^{(1)} - \sigma_\theta^{(1)}) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}}{\partial \theta} = 0, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \sigma_\theta^{(1)}}{\partial \theta} + \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}}{\partial r} + \frac{2}{r} \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)} = 0. \quad (23)$$

Thus, an expression for the boundary conditions for the stresses $\sigma_{ij}^{(1)}$ is obtained. The fluctuating normal to the cavity contour is obtained as a decomposition by vectors \bar{e}_r and \bar{e}_θ , where \bar{e}_r and \bar{e}_θ are unit vectors directed along the coordinate lines of the polar coordinate system $(\bar{e}_r, \bar{e}_\theta)$. Taking into account fluctuations of the normal to the excavation contour, we have the following expression:

$$(\sigma_\theta^{(0)} + \epsilon \sigma_\theta^{(1)}) \frac{\bar{e}_\theta}{r_0} \frac{dH}{d\theta} + (\tau_{r\theta}^{(0)} + \epsilon \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}) \frac{\bar{e}_\theta}{r_0} \frac{dH}{d\theta} = 0. \quad (24)$$

Eq. (22) can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_\theta^{(1)} = \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \sigma_r^{(1)}) - \frac{\partial \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)}}{\partial \theta}. \quad (25)$$

Once the ring within which the boundary fluctuates is identified, the following conditions are observed: $\sigma_r^{(1)} = 0$ at $r = r_0$; $\sigma_\theta^{(1)} = \langle \sigma_\theta \rangle$ at $r > r_0$. The ring experiences compression with effective properties under the action of P_0 .

In the zero approximation, $\sigma_{rr}^{(0)}$ can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_2} = -P_0, \quad \sigma_{rr}^{(0)} \Big|_{r=r_1} = 0 \quad (26)$$

where $r_1 = r_0 - \frac{H}{2}$ and $r_2 = r_0 + \frac{H}{2}$. Subsequently, $\sigma_{rr}^{(0)}$, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(0)}$ and $u_r^{(0)}$ can be expressed as:

$$\begin{cases} \sigma_{rr}^{(0)} = P_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_1^2}{r^2}\right) \left(\frac{r_2^2}{r^2} - 1\right)^{-1}, \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(0)} = -P_0 \left(1 - \frac{r_1^2}{r^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{r_2^2}{r^2}\right)^{-1}, \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} u_r^{(0)} &= \frac{C_1}{2r} + C_2 r, \\ C_1 &= P_0 V_0^2 \left(\mu \left(\frac{r_1^2}{r_2^2} - 1 \right) \right)^{-1}, \\ C_2 &= P_0 \left(2(\lambda + \eta) \left(\frac{r_1^2}{r_2^2} - 1 \right) \right)^{-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

At $P_0 = k \left(1 - \left(\frac{r_1^2}{r_2^2} \right) \right)$, plasticity occurs at the point $r = r_1$, and the stress state at the points $r = r_1$ can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(0)} = k \left(\frac{r_1^2}{r^2} - 1 \right), \quad \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(0)} = k \left(\frac{r_1^2}{r^2} + 1 \right). \quad (29)$$

The roughness of the cavity in the form of a fractal Weierstrass function is obtained as [12, 13]:

$$H(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b^n \sin(a^n \theta), \quad b > 1, \quad a > 1. \quad (30)$$

Then, substituting Eqs. (26), (27) into Eq. (30), it can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_{rr}^{(1)} = \frac{r_1^2}{r} H \left(\frac{r_1^2 p}{r_2^2 - r_1^2} \right)^{-1} (\sin 2\theta + \cos 2\theta), \quad (31)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{r\theta}^{(1)} &= \frac{r_1^2}{r} \left[\frac{H}{2} \left(\frac{r_1^2 p}{r_2^2 - r_1^2} \right)^{-1} (-\sin 2\theta + \cos 2\theta - 1) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{dH}{d\theta} r^2 \right], \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta}^{(1)} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Thus, it has been determined that in the vicinity of the cavity, shear stresses arise, leading to stress concentration and the potential for reaching the limit of plastic or brittle states. This behavior becomes irregular within the layer surrounding the cavity, occurring locally at certain angles θ . Consequently, it may result in the loss of geometric stability of the rock contour of the cavity, leading to rock formations falling out along a localized system of slip lines or cracks, whose direction can be predicted. The “weak spots” near the cavity contour represent zones where plastic or brittle fracture energy localizes. Fractal structures present or formed in the rock massif with the cavity alter the

geometry of the underground space not only locally but also in macroscopic volumes through the effective physical and mechanical properties of the geomaterials [14].

4. Some estimates of the influence of fractality on the elastic modulus of rock mass

Fractal structure identification can be achieved through various theoretical, numerical, and experimental approaches. The model of an inhomogeneous elastic medium enables the calculation of effective modules using different methods. However, the available structure models that facilitate determining the fractal nature of the composite, estimating the fractal dimensionality, and using it to refine formulas for effective modules are limited. Nevertheless, a method for calculating the correlation functions of elastic coefficients has been developed for certain structures [14, 30].

The correlation function is defined as:

$$R(r) = \langle \lambda'(r_1) \lambda'(r_1 + r) \rangle \quad (33)$$

where $\lambda(r_1)$ is the fluctuation of the elastic coefficients $\lambda(r_1)$ from the average value $\langle \lambda \rangle$. The indicator function is expressed as:

$$\Omega(r) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{with probability } \lambda, \\ 0 & \text{with probability } 1 - \lambda. \end{cases} \quad (34)$$

The correlation function can be expressed in terms of the probabilities that the points r_1 and $r_1 + r$ have elements belonging to the same cluster, such as microdamages like micropores or microcracks. It is known that for large r in the lattice model of the discontinuum [12, 34], the correlation function is approximated by the power of the distance, expressed as:

$$R(r) \sim r^{-\alpha} \quad (35)$$

where the value α is determined by the difference between the Euclidean dimension of space D and

the fractal dimension of the cluster D_* . The value α is obtained as:

$$\alpha = D - D_* \tag{36}$$

Thus, D_* can be estimated using the Witten–Meekin method. As mentioned earlier, the density of the fractal structure changes in proportion to the distance (radius) from the center of mass of the cluster, which can be determined by Eq. (8). The highest density of material occurs where, for example, the layered structure is well-defined, with near-order, correlation, and density remaining constant in this part of the cluster. In the far-order zone, the correlation and density decrease, following the linear law, as observed in the scaling relation in the sample of the layered structure [38]. To estimate the fractal dimension, we can use a dependency graph $R(r)$ or $\rho(r)$ (see Fig. 2).

In Fig. 2, the following notations are used: r_{loc} is the radius of the local order region; R_{clas} is the cluster radius; ρ_{max} , $\langle \rho \rangle$, ρ_{min} represent the maximum, average, and minimum densities, respectively. ρ_{min} can be obtained as: $\rho_{min} = \rho_{loc} - (\rho_{max} - \langle \rho \rangle)$. The estimate of α can be obtained from the following relation:

$$(\rho_{max} - \rho_{min}) \sim (R_{clas} - r_{loc})^{-\alpha} \tag{37}$$

The values of ρ_{max} , ρ_{min} , R_{clas} , r_{loc} in Eq. (37) are determined experimentally, and then α is found. By substituting α into Eq. (36), D_* can be obtained.

Calculation of the effective elastic modulus of bodies with a fractal structure is performed using various methods, including the self-consistent field method [14, 30, 39]. For instance, estimates of the jump conductivity effect and analytical dependencies near critical concentration were obtained for resistance or conductivity based on percolation models by nodes and bonds. In elastic models, the dependence on damage concentration (e.g., disseminated microcracks) or on crack length in the case of concentrated damage is considered. Near the critical concentration, the elastic modules show a characteristic dependence as in

FIG. 2: Dependence of density $\rho(r)$ on the distance between structural elements.

Eqs. (10), (11), (12), while outside the vicinity of the critical concentration p_c , the dependence of elastic models on concentration is described according to an appropriate calculation scheme (see Figs.3 and 4). C_m^{max} and C_m^{min} are the upper and lower values of the estimates calculated using the mixing theory, respectively. C_s^{max} and C_s^{min} are the upper and lower values of the estimates calculated using the self-consistent field method, respectively. $C_k^{(1)}$ and $C_k^{(2)}$ are the percolation thresholds. G_{ef} is the effective elastic modulus, and G_1 is the elastic modulus of the first component of the composite.

The generalizations of continuum models include considerations of the influence of the distribution of elastic and density properties of natural and artificial objects in the medium on its metric properties and curvature of space, based on Einstein’s ideas. Within the Newtonian approach (field theory), classical CM equations can be obtained from this generalization. In models associated with the Einstein approach, continuum deformation, which is usually associated with the use of Lagrangian and Eulerian coordinates in classical models, is calculated using deformation incompatibility relations, effectively extending the continuum model to the discontinuum. This allows for the description of rock massifs with underground structures. The second factor

FIG. 3: (Color online) Typical dependence of the dimensionless shear modulus G_{ef}/G_1 (vertical axis) for a two-component composite on the concentration of the first component C_1 (horizontal axis).

influencing the physical-mechanical properties and the stress-strain state of the medium is related to the use of the Mandelbrot approach, which involves fractal models of deterministic and stochastic types. The fractal approach accounts for the fractional dimensionality of structures inherent in real materials, influencing the distribution of stresses and strains in the boundary layers, both external and internal. Fractal models of damage clusters, such as micropores, microcracks, and dislocations, enable the description of macroscopic crack formation based on percolation theory models. The cracking process occurs when the damage concentration reaches a critical value, resembling a phase transition in the considered medium volume.

5. Conclusions

The application of the Newton approach based on field and potential theory confines the set of field functions to smooth functions (differentiable), which is typical for continuum models. Utilization of fractal structures and

FIG. 4: (Color online) Dependence of the dimensionless effective shear modulus G_{ef}/G (vertical axis) on the concentration of microcracks C (horizontal axis) aggregated into a crack. G is the shear modulus without cracks.

functions allows for creation of more realistic models for rocks and underground structures. Technogenic structures, including underground constructions, locally alter the metric and dimensionality of space, which makes it necessary to use fractal models. It is considered that the actual non-ideality (roughness) of the excavation surface (contour) leads to the development of shear stresses, which affects the stress concentration, strength and bearing capacity of the excavation. The influence of fractal structures in rocks on effective physical-mechanical properties (elastic modules) is evident in the percolation effect, associated with scattered or concentrated fracture within the considered volume. The method of determining the percolation threshold is the node or bond method, which indicates the critical damage concentration or crack length. The fractal dimensionality and percolation threshold allow the derivation of analytical relationships describing elastic modules concerning damage concentration near the threshold. On the other hand, the relationships beyond the threshold region are determined using the self-consistent

field method. In the case of a model of a horizontal cavity (excavation) bounded by a cylindrical surface with non-smoothness described by the Weierstrass fractal function, the shear stresses are calculated. This study can potentially aid in solving problems related to stress concentration and ultimate loads.

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Compliance with ethical standards

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